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A REVIEW ANDROID CAMPUS GUIDE FOR MAUTECH, YOLA NIGERIA

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Abstract

Considering most of our Universities that have a stationary campus map at their main entrance which in most cases is outdated; with a campus that is expanding in size and in its number of buildings, locating those buildings can be very tedious especially for someone new to the campus. This paper proposed a campus guide for Modibbo Adama University of technology, Yola (MAUTECH). The MAUTECH Android Campus Guide application is developed to address the problems of freshman student waste of time in looking for offices, lecture theatres and departments. It will also serve as a navigation system for interested persons who would like to move from place to place on the campus but do not know how. An application was developed to serve primarily as a means to serve as a navigation guide to facilitate movement around the University campus. The application does this by serving as an information repository where people can easily discover more about the facilities and staff/faculty contained in Modibbo Adama University of Technology Yola. Also with the integration of Google Maps into the application, moving around the campus for new comers and other visitors is made more convenient. This research will be a useful tool in the recruitment of students and during campus events (matriculation and convocation ceremonies) where there is a large influx of visitors on the campus. The application was designed with the view of providing maximum simplicity, quality user experience; create user interface and most importantly accurate data.

Keywords: Internet, Android, Model, Guide, Campus -Map

Introduction

Mobile applications (usually referred as “apps”), are considered to be one of the fastest growing trends in Information Systems industry (Eddy, 2011). Users enjoy the variety of features that mobile apps can provide quickly and without introducing unnecessary complexity into their designs. As a result, mobile apps present a more popular interface frontier action with business systems than using web applications via Web Browser. Smartphone tablets and wireless data plans are already a trillion dollar a year business. However this is just the beginning. More and more students are interested in Mobile Computing.

The Android application, a campus guide system, is a practice in mobile development. There are two major platforms in the mobile device community: iOS and Android. This project chose Android development, mainly for the reason of its openness. In addition, all the tools in the Android development are free and no special hardware is required. Application components are the essential building blocks of an Android application. There are four different types of application components. Each type serves a distinct purpose and has its own lifecycle that defines how the component is created and destroyed. One of the application components is Activity. An activity represents a single screen with a user interface. A multi-screen application will consist of a number of activities that work together to form a cohesive user experience. This research uses fragments in the activity to support dynamic and flexible user interface. It also applies the navigation-drawer pattern and sliding pane layout from the responsive pattern in different places to handle multi-panes interactions. This mobile application intends to provide information about a university campus to a tourist using his/her current location. When the user opens the app in his/her mobile device, there will be a map showing the overall view of the campus. The user can center the map over an area of interest, zoom in on that area to get detailed information, or select one or more buildings in the campus to visit. The application will be able to navigate the user to a point of interest. In addition, detailed information about a building, such as the name, the services provided, the residing departments, and current events hosted in the building, can be obtained by the user

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The ModibboAdama University of Technology, Yola (MAUTECH) is a very large institution with many departments on different Locations. In this regard, it is often the case that new comers (freshman students, new staff, and visitors) may find navigation around the school’s campus difficult as they are not able to figure out how to get to their desired locations on campus. This class of people would benefit from Android Campus Guide that would serve as a navigation guide to take them around the campus

easily. The proposed system will alleviate this problem and cut-down the amount of time spent when new comers or visitors are trying to get to a particular location on the campus.

Objective

The MAUTECH Android Campus Guide application will be develop to address the problems of freshman student waste of time in looking for lecture theatre and departments. Therefore to that end, the aim of the application is three-fold.

(i).It would serve as a guide for the MAUTECH community to determine if there is significant difference between the proposed mobile application and verbal communication in finding location on the campus in terms of reliability, accuracy and accessibility. This would enable members of the MAUTECH community, especially Freshmen and new Staff, to locate offices and other points of interest easier.

(ii).The application would serve as a means to advertise the school to interested persons and, therefore, increase the awareness of the resrouces MAUTECH has (excellent Technology and facilities, dedicated staff and top-notch departments) among such persons.

(iii). Being a navigation system, the application would assist new comers move more easily around MAUTECH campus.

The Significant of the Study

Android campus guide is one of the things inside the campus that the students rely on to locate places on the campus with ease, yet it is ignored to be more modernized given that technology is incorporated nowadays. This is one of the main initiatives of the proponents in the development of the System. The application can be accessed through internet connection (preferably Wi-Fi). Given that Android Technology supports various models of smart phones and tablets. This study aims to target the benefits of the following entities:

- To integrate virtual map that will pinpoint specific location to the user.
To provide the visitors and staff with information regarding the selected location.
- To reduce freshman student waste of time in looking for lecture theatre and departments.
- Wrong information on the direction that was given by the people being asked by New staffs and Visitors.
- To determine if there is significant difference between the proposed mobile application and verbal communication in finding location in terms of reliability, accuracy and accessibility.

Review of Literature

Android is a relatively new platform. It is produced by Google, Inc., and its first release was presented in 2007 (Meier, 2010). Android is installed on many different mobile devices and its users can download Android apps and other content through Google Play service, which replaced the old Android Market (Bishop, 2012). This project discusses technologies incorporated in Android application development and how they apply to the research problem. As the official Android website describes this platform, "Android is a software stack for mobile devices that includes an operating system, middleware and key applications" ("What is Android," 2012). Android provides the "core set of applications including an email client, SMS program, calendar, maps, browser, contacts, and others" ("What is Android," 2012), while additional applications can be downloaded through Google Play service (Bishop, 2012).

Google (n.d.) claims that "Android powers millions of phones, tablets and other devices. "Phones and tablets are mobile devices that can have Android applications installed on them. These applications are written in Java programming language ("What is Android," 2012) and they are called mobile device applications or apps. Development techniques for apps are structured sets of Java code focused on implementing particular task that provides content for a mobile device application. Although Java programming language includes a broad variety of topics, this project focuses on development techniques required for successful implementation of Android Campus guide for Mautech. The following paragraphs analyze research efforts that addressed these techniques in the past.

Android Fundamentals

Many authors described Android application development fundamentals, which include setting up Android development environment on the machine, AndroidManifest.xml file, Activities, Intents, and XML layouts. Jackson (2011) outlines "three major components of an Android development environment: Java, Eclipse, Android" and provides instructions on how to download and install necessary files to establish this environment. Felker (2011) does not explicitly state the components but rather points out that Java JDK, Android SDK, Eclipse IDE, and Android ADT need to be installed and configured on a machine. The steps provided by these two authors are standard. They appear in many books written on Android development and are also presented on official Android website ("Installing the SDK", n.d.). Ableson, King, and Sen (2011) present "four primary components of Android applications": Activity, Service, Broadcast Receiver, and Content Provider. It is

noted that “a particular Android application might not contain all of these elements, but will have at least one of these elements” (Ableson, King, and Sen, 2011).

Since Activity “displays a UI (user interface) and responds to system and user initiated events” (Ableson, King, and Sen, 2011), it is used very frequently for Android applications. These Activities are declared in `AndroidManifest.xml` file, which provides “the foundation for any Android application” (Murphy, 2011). Activities present their views through XML layouts and “communicate” with each other through Intents. Clear understanding of these concepts and Java programming language is a prerequisite to start implementing the development techniques used in Android applications.

Android Fragment

Android introduced fragments in Android 3.0(APIlevel11). A Fragment represents a behavior or a portion of a user interface in an Activity. We combine multiple fragments in a single activity to build a multi-pane user interface. The fragment information can be reused in the activity. For example: when a campus map is displayed in the designated panel, the user can move the building of interest. To the center of the map. The user can then click to view the detailed information about the building. When the user returns to the previous screen, the selected building still remains in the center of the map. The fragment is able to “remember” previous screen information. Without the use of fragments, the activity has to call for instructions to store and retain the Previous actions, to recreate the view in order to have same screen layout.

Prior Research

Contributions of prior research efforts provide useful information for successful implementation of Android campus guide application. This project analyzes how to determine which development technique to use for a particular feature, what are the steps to implement each technique, and whether they can be applied for Android campus guide-related data. Testing of the official Android campus guide app has shown that it provides some of the pre-selected features for Android Mobile application like Twitter Updates, Online Directory, Athletics News, and Campus Map. Implementation steps for development techniques required are explored in various Android development books and Internet tutorials. Since a majority of Android campus guide content is obtained from the Web, this section reflects existing development techniques that enable gathering online data. Steele (2011) provides “recipes” for using web content, such as “Customizing a Web Browser,” “Using an HTTP GET,” or “Using HTTPPOST.” Steele (2011) suggests that “a separate thread should be spawned anytime network data is required” and he uses *AsyncTask* class for this. Murphy (2011) describes the steps on how to use *AsyncTask* class, which include creation of an *AsyncTask* subclass, overriding one or more of its methods, creating an instance of *AsyncTask* subclass, and executing it. These steps can be implemented anytime *AsyncTask* class is needed, and Vogel (2010b) provides a working example of *AsyncTask* class implementation in his tutorial.

Jordan and Greyling (2011) combine some ideas presented in previous paragraph. For their instructions, they first describe a particular Android problem, briefly illustrate the solution (development technique), and finally explain in detail how it works. They provide 8 “recipes” on “Displaying Web Information” and many others (Jordan and Greyling, 2011). This approach generates step-by-step instructions for specific development techniques and shows working examples of them. Collecting information from Twitter uses some of the techniques mentioned, such as Steele’s (2011) “Using an HTTP GET” and Murphy’s (2011) instructions for *AsyncTask* class. With *AsyncTask* class and HTTP GET request already in place, retrieving Twitter data can be accomplished through Twitter API (Bradby, 2011). Data returned from the Twitter API are in JSON format (Bradby, 2011), which can be parsed to store desired information.

Existing Literature Deficiencies

Although the majority of the research completed on Android development techniques is very comprehensive, existing literature still lacks support for project problems. These deficiencies are explored throughout the research for this project and explained in the following paragraphs.

Available instructions would require a certain degree of customization to adjust them for all data sources and connection types. This is especially evident for data sources that require a secure connection. There is a need for establishing a development technique determination process to provide guidelines.

Techniques currently available do not provide all necessary step-by-step instructions. Systems change in different environments, and development techniques cannot be applied the same way every time. In addition to this, security policies vary as well. Step by-step instructions for accessing data through Android Campus Guide App Self-Services, mautech.edu.ng, and others would provide directions for successful implementation of pre-selected features. It cannot be stated with certainty that all Android Campus Guide features can be implemented. The documentation on the official Android campus guide app is unavailable. An Internet search does not provide examples of Android Campus Guide applications that exploit preselected features not implemented in official Android Campus Guide app. Therefore, it can be concluded that while some of the Android Campus Guide features can be created for Mautech, the successful completion of all of them is still uncertain. The following chapters investigate these problems and provide solutions to them.

System Analysis and Design

The purpose of the system analysis and design is to show the types of methods and methodology used in the development of this project. A method is the way in which you complete a task or the steps taken in completing a task. Methodology is the systematic, theoretical analysis of the methods applied in a field of study or the principles associated with a branch of knowledge.

Requirements

To ensure that the right software was built, requirements were gathered to specify the functionality of the application (functional requirements) as well as limitations regarding how the application was to operate (non-functional requirements). It is worth noting that over the course of developing the application, more requirements were added to the requirements that we gathered initially as a result of the software development approach that we took to develop the software. The requirements listed below represents the set of requirements, upon which the final version of the software was built and not on the requirements that were initially elicited. These requirements were gathered with the use of a variety of techniques including interviews, meetings and surveys.

Functional Requirements

The functionality of the application is governed by the following functional requirements:

- The user can read the description of a building on campus
 - The user can view pictures of a building on campus
 - The user can view offices in a building on campus
 - The user can read textual directions to the building on campus
 - The user can see the building's position on Google Maps
 - The user can automatically get directions to the building on Google Maps
 - The user can read textual directions to offices within a building
 - The user can read a description of an office within a building
 - The user can view the staff contained within an office in a building
 - The user can view the contact information of the staff in an office
 - The user can email the staff in an office
 - The user can read the bio of staff within an office
 - The user can view the courses that a staff offers

Non-Functional Requirements

Limitations regarding how the application is to implement the above stated functional requirements are enumerated below

- **Look and Feel Requirements**

The Mautech logo and a map of Mautech and its surrounding areas should be displayed. It should be obvious from merely looking at the application display that it is a Mautech related application. The client for the product and other stakeholders should find the application visually and aesthetically appealing. This should be done with design and coloring that is comforting and not distracting. The appearance of the application should not deter the user from its purpose.

- **Usability and Human Requirements**

- The application should be easy to use.
- Terms used in the application should be familiar with the users. Further explanation should be provided for terminology that is Mautech specific in order to ensure that users who are not part of the Mautech community are still able to use the application.
- The application will be made available on platforms that are easily accessed by members of the Mautech community and potential members of the Mautech community (new departments, staff and students).

- **Performance Requirements**

- The application's functionality should be reliable and available to the users at all times. It would be helpful to make the application an offline application so that people without constant and/or reliable internet connectivity can still use the application.
- The application should be able to handle all inputs provided by the user and provide output in a timely manner.
- **Operational Requirements**
- Since this application is android based and can be used offline, it should work on android phones with or without internet access. The application should work on a version of android that is still in use - but not recent - as well as other later versions of android following that version.
- **Maintainability Requirements**
- The application should be easily updated in the case that new buildings and offices are added to the Mautech campus
- **Security Requirements**
- Given the functionality of the application, security measures are not necessary, as there is no important user data that could be compromised.
- **Cultural, Political and Legal Requirements**
- The Mautech community is multi-cultural and diverse. Potential members of the Mautech community come from even more diverse settings. As such an application should be designed so that there is little room for a cultural interpretation of the elements displayed in the application.

Platform Requirements

Two of the most integral tools used in developing this application are;

- **Android Studio**
- Android Studio is the primary integrated development environment for developing native Android applications. Android Studio is available freely under the Apache License 2.0 and was developed based on the Jet Brains' IntelliJ IDEA software. It runs on the most popular Operating System platforms and substituted Eclipse Android Development Tools as the basis for developing Android applications. Our application was built using Android Studio.
- **GitHub**
- GitHub is a web-based hosting service that allows revision control and source code management. It facilitates collaboration on projects with features such as bug tracking, task management, and feature requests. GitHub allowed us to work on our project without having to be physically together. It also enabled us to involve third party coders to help us out whenever we face challenges while developing software.
- **Heroes of Might and Magic Map Editor**
- Heroes of Might and Magic Map Editor was the software that was used to design the application main screen. The software is a map editor for a game where users can drag and drop items – buildings, soldiers, trees etc. - to create fictional villages for use in the Heroes of Might and Magic Game. We used the map editor to create a rendition of the main campus of Mautech.

Analysis Model

Analysis Modeling combines text and diagramming to depict the requirements of a given software in a way that is easily understood and reviewed. Analysis modelling can be accomplished in a variety of ways including; UML-Based Modeling, Scenario-Based Modeling, Behavioral Modeling, Data Modelling etc. To make this application, we employed UML-Based modeling techniques – specifically Use Case diagrams and Activity Diagrams- to make sense of our gathered requirements.

Use Case

A Use Case Diagram represents a user's interaction with a system in a manner that shows the relationship the user has with the different use cases that the user is involved in. Figure 1 Use Case diagrams can depict the ways multiple users interact with a system as well as the different use cases that each user is associated with.

Figure 1: Use Case Diagram

Use Case Descriptions

1.	Tap Location
2.	Read Location's Description
3.	View Location's Images
4.	View Offices in Location
5.	Read Location's Direction
6.	View Location on Google Maps
7.	Get Directions to Location on Google maps
8.	View Office's Directions
9.	View Staff in Office
10.	View Offices Description
11.	Send Email to Staff
12.	View Staff's Bio
13.	View Staff's Courses

Table 1: List of Use Cases

SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE

The Software Architecture defines how the different components of a software will be arranged and how they will operate and interact with one another. The application makes use of the Model View Controller Architecture, with elements of the Call and Return Architecture present as well. In the Call and Return Architecture, there is a single thread of control with the software organized hierarchically in terms of routines and subroutines. However, the Call and Return Architecture plays a very miniscule role in terms of the structural organization of the software.

MODEL VIEW CONTROLLER**Figure 2: Model View Controller Pattern**

Figure 2 shows the Model View Controller (MVC): is a three tier software architecture that splits the User interface (View) from the database (model) but uses a “middleman” (Controller) to connect the two. An integral advantage of the MVC architecture is that it enables each constituent part of the MVC to do its own job.

Android applications make heavy use of the MVC architecture and android campus guide application is no different. In the case of android campus guide application, the user interface that the user interacts with is the View. This was defined by resources and layouts in Android Studio that is in XML format. These determined how the application would be laid out to the user. The SQLite database that our software works with represents the view for the application. The database is populated with information regarding the various entities of the application. The controller – the activities that we programmed - collects information from the user’s actions on the view and retrieves information from the database based on that user’s action, and displays that information to the user on the view. The Model View Pattern is evident in the way the application is structured in Android Studio as well As can be seen in the image above, the entities make up the Model, while the .xml files make up the View and the activities – which serves as the controller – determines how the model interacts with the View.

Design Considerations

Based on the gathered requirements and the software architecture, the application is to be designed in the following manner. The design goals of the system include performance, dependability and end user criteria.

Performance

The application will be used by anyone who wishes to learn about MAUTECH or navigate around it. Since the database that the application works with sits on the device on which it runs, the only limitation to the application’s performance is the internet connection of the user. This would come into play when loading pictures for a facility and connecting to Google Maps to find directions to a building.

Dependability

The application is easily modifiable so that the information it presents can be adjusted at any time. In the event that the location of offices changes or that new buildings are created, the application can be updated easily to reflect these changes. The application is dependable as it has been rid of all its bugs. Thus, users will not be subject to application crashes. However, as some of the application’s functionality requires an internet connection, the application may not be so dependable in the event that a user needs to navigate around the school but lacks internet.

End User Criteria

The end users - freshman students, visitors, etc. – will find the system easy to use as it is intuitive and simple.

Entity Relationship Diagram

Figure 3 is the Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD) of the application. It was designed using the Visual Paradigm software.

Figure 3: ER - Diagram

The ERD above represents three of the most important entities in the application – Facility, Office, and Staff. As the diagram depicts, there is a one to many relationship between Facility and Office, and a one to many relationship between Office and Staff. This means that every Facility contains one or more offices while every office contains one or more staff. It is also shown above that the Staff entity has a foreign key that links it with the Office entity and that the Office entity has foreign key that links it with the Facility entity. This demonstrates that a Staff would belong to a unique Office while, Offices would belong to a unique Facility

Software Methodology

Based on the design considerations, the details of how the application was built are detailed in this section. For the creation of the application, we employed the agile approach to software development showed in below as figure 4. We developed the application based on constant feedback from our client and other interested persons in the application.

Figure 4: Agile Software Development

An example of this was in the development of our user interface. After gathering the requirements for the application we decided it was best to draw a rendition of the university’s main campus that showed how the university would look like if seen from above. After making this drawing however, we deemed it as not good enough. After a few other renditions, we decided to settle on using the map Editor for a game called Heroes of Might and Magic to make an intuitive rendition of the main campus. The way the main screen of our application was designed also shares parallels with the construction of other parts of the application.

Activity Diagram

Figure 5: The Activity Diagram below shows how all the gathered requirements and use cases were implemented in the application and it also represents the workflow of the application.

Figure 5: Activity Diagram

As is shown in the Activity Diagram, when the user opens the application, they are presented with a screen where they can tap on a representation of any of the buildings on the school’s main campus. From this screen, the user can either decide to press the back button to exit the application or tap on one of the buildings. If the user taps on one of the buildings, they are shown another screen where they can get directions to the Location on Google Maps, view the location’s description, read the location’s directions, view offices contained within the location, and view the location on Google Maps. From this screen, the user can either decide to press the back button which takes him to the previous screen where he can tap on another building, or the user can tap on one of the offices.

When the user taps on one of the offices, he is taken to another screen where he can view the office’s description, view the staff in an office, and read descriptions of the office. At this point, the user can tap on the back button which takes them to the previous screen where they can tap on another office or they can tap on a staff.

When the user taps on a staff, they are presented with a screen where they can send an email to the staff, read the staff’s bio, view the staff’s courses, and view the staff’s contact information. From this screen, the user can decide to press the back button which takes them back to the previous screen where they can tap on another staff member.

MAUTECH Campus Guide

Figure 6: Screenshot of Application shows how the application appear. This section will discuss the application and the functionality that has been implemented in the application. On the Application Menu of the user device, the application shown with the logo of ModibboAdama university of Nigeria as its icon and it is called Campus Guide. On the screenshot above, it is the first application on the second row with a white background. Once the user taps on this icon, the application MAUTECH Campus Guide.

Figure 7: Screenshot of Application

If the User decides to tap on the representation of Arts and Sciences, they are taken to the screen depicted above. Here they can view the building on Google Maps, read about the building, see pictures of the building as well as see a list of offices that are contained within the building. If the user wishes to get directions to the building from their current location, then he taps the marker on the Arts and Sciences Building on Google Maps which then brings up two more buttons. If the user taps on the button with the white arrow inside a blue diamond, then they are taken to the Google maps application where he is automatically shown a route to the building from his current position.

Conclusion

The aim of this project was to produce an android campus guide application for mobile devices that would allow navigation for interested persons who would like to move from place to place on the campus but do not know how. The aim was also to improve upon the ideas of other existing systems. The project has grown through further research and this report details the introduction research and design of the system and well as the implementation and testing of the system.

Review on Android Campus Guide, location methods, review of mobile devices, Mobile application and a review of existing applications was conducted. The design methodology and analysis of the system was reported. Problems of existing system were

mention as well as the proposed solutions from this new system. The functional and non-functional requirements, features of this new system, the flow of operation of the system were documented.

In conclusion the objectives of this system were fulfilled. All the requirements hashed out were met. An application was developed to serve primarily as a means to serve as a navigation guide to facilitate movement around the University campus. The application does this by serving as an information repository where people can easily discover more about the facilities and staff/faculty contained in Modibbo Adama University of Technology Yola. Also with the integration of Google Maps into the application, moving around the campus for new comers and other visitors is made more convenient. Over the course of working on the project, i faced a lot of challenges and in effect to that I learned a number of lessons.

I will as well recommend that the application should be used in the recruitment of new students, staff and faculty and that it should also be used in the Orientation of Freshman students when a new semester begins. It can also be available to visitors who would wish to navigate around the campus.

REFERENCES

- [1] Felker, D. (2011). *Android Application Development For Dummies*. Hoboken, NJ. Wiley Publishing, Inc.
- [2] ("Installing the SDK", n.d.). Ableson, King, and Sen (2011) present "four primary components of Android applications":
- [3] Eddy, N. (2011, December 8). "Cloud Computing: Cloud, Mobile Apps, Public Storage Are Top IT Trends for 2012 and Beyond: Gartner". Retrieved from <http://www.eweek.com/c/a/Cloud-Computing/Cloud-Mobile-Apps-Public-Storage->.
- [4] Activity "displays a UI (user interface) and responds to system and user initiated events" (Ableson, King, and Sen, 2011).
- [5] Steele (2011) provides "recipes" for using web content, such as "Customizing a Web Browser," "Using an HTTP GET," or "Using HTTP POST."
- [6] Steele (2011) suggests that "a separate thread should be spawned anytime network data is required" and he uses *AsyncTask*class for this
- [7] Murphy (2011) describes the steps on how to use *AsyncTask*class, which include creation of an *AsyncTask*subclass, overriding one or more of its methods, creating an instance of *AsyncTask*subclass, and executing it.
- [8] and Vogel (2010b) provides a working example of *AsyncTask*class implementation in his tutorial.
- [9] They provide 8"recipes" on "Displaying Web Information" and many others (Jordan and Greyling, 2011).
- [10] Data returned from the Twitter API are in JSON format (Bradby, 2011), which can be parsed to store desired information.
- [11] Android is a relatively new platform. It is produced by Google, Inc., and its first release was presented in 2007 (Meier, 2010).
- [12] Android is installed on many different mobile devices and its users can download Android apps and other content through Google Play service, which replaced the old Android Market (Bishop, 2012).
- [13] Android provides the "core set of applications including an email client, SMS program, calendar, maps, browser, contacts, and others" ("What is Android," 2012),
- [14]. Jackson (2011) outlines "three major components of an Android development environment: Java, Eclipse, Android" and provides instructions on how to download and install necessary files to establish this environment.
- [15] Ableson, King, and Sen (2011) present "four primary components of Android applications": Activity, Service, BroadcastReceiver, and ContentProvider. It is noted that "a particular Android application might not contain all of these elements, but will have at least one of these elements"

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